

AI Nurses Network: Building a clinical research network on artificial intelligence in nursing

Siobhan O'Connor¹[0000-0001-8579-1718], Crina Grosan¹[0000-0003-1049-2136], Rebecca Oakey²[0000-0003-2706-8139], Xiaoyang Li¹[0009-0006-3695-9485], Mengying Zhang¹[0000-0001-9802-4913], Emma Stanmore³[0000-0002-4522-5292], David Woodcock⁴[1111-2222-3333-4444], Suzanne Bench^{5,6}[0000-0002-4499-2959]

¹*Florence Nightingale Faculty of Nursing, Midwifery and Palliative Care, King's College London, United Kingdom*

²*Faculty of Life Sciences and Medicine, King's College London, United Kingdom*

³*School of Health Sciences, The University of Manchester, United Kingdom*

⁴*Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) representative*

⁵*Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust, London, United Kingdom*

⁶*London South Bank University, London, United Kingdom*

siobhan.oconnor@kcl.ac.uk

Abstract. Artificial intelligence (AI) is being used more often in healthcare, but nurses lack knowledge and skills in AI which can prevent them from taking part in or leading research on AI in healthcare that could improve patient care. A new clinical research network on AI in nursing, the AI Nurses Network, was established to offer education and training, seed funding, and networking opportunities to nurses across the United Kingdom to build more capacity for digitally enabled nurses and AI research and practice in the National Health Service (NHS).

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, nursing informatics, nursing education

1 Introduction

Scientific research has shown that nurses lack knowledge and skills in artificial intelligence (AI), with few nurses actively involved in or leading AI research in healthcare [1]. Nurses' low awareness and poor understanding of AI limits their ability to introduce AI tools into clinical practice that could improve care, it prevents them from educating patients and families about the benefits, limitations and risks of AI and AI-based technologies, and it reduces their opportunities to take part in and lead AI research which can slow nurses' professional development and limit their career opportunities long-term.

In 2021, the Chief Nursing Officer for England launched a new strategic plan for research which emphasised the importance of generating and translating nurse led research to underpin the development of digitally enabled practice environments [2]. A review of digital health research conducted by nurses in England revealed limited research on AI in nursing and recommended more investment and funding to support

nurses to conduct digital health research [3]. Therefore, the world's first clinical research network on AI in nursing was established in 2024 to support the development of the nursing informatics workforce in the NHS across the United Kingdom.

2 Methods

The AI Nurses Network has a range of resources to support nurses to learn and apply AI techniques and AI tools in clinical research and professional practice to enhance patient care and population health (<https://www.ai-nurses.com/>). Firstly, it offers education and training opportunities on AI from machine learning to natural language processing and more to equip nurses with the necessary knowledge and skills to lead and participate in AI research. This includes an existing Innovation Scholars programme that provides big data skills training for the health workforce across three fundamental pillars (i.e., data science, genomics and AI) funded by UKRI (Table 1).

Table 1. Innovation Scholars programme

Pillar 1 – Health data science	Pillar 2 – Genomics	Pillar 3 – Artificial intelligence
Introduction to Python for Health Research	Spreadsheets	Demystifying AI
AI in Health Analytics	R Basics	Intermediate Python and Software Engineering
Machine Learning for Health Research	Statistics with R	Applied AI
Introduction to R	Advanced R (coming soon)	AI ethics (coming soon)
Prediction Modelling		
Introduction to Statistics		
Natural Language Processing for Health Research		

Along with this free online training, the network is hosting bespoke online training seminars where nurses can get practical support with preparing a health dataset for predictive modelling, choosing appropriate algorithms and other AI techniques to apply to the data to develop an AI model, and how to validate predictive models.

Secondly, the clinical research network is providing seed funding to kickstart a number of innovative research projects led by nurses that pioneer AI in an area of healthcare to improve patient care or population health. It is also supporting an undergraduate nursing student to join the team for a summer scholarship to learn more about the development and application of AI in healthcare to help further their career opportunities and build research capacity in nursing.

Thirdly, the network runs its own in person and online events to foster connections among nurses, AI researchers, and AI industry leaders and promotes events from the

Alan Turing Institute and King's AI Institute to facilitate the exchange of ideas and support collaborations for nurse-led research in AI. For example, a hackathon focused on AI in nursing is also being organised and will be held in London in September 2025. This will enable nurses to brainstorm AI solutions to a current health challenge with researchers and industry partners. The network also started a monthly webinar series where nurses from around the world discuss their use of AI in education, clinical practice, research or policy. These are hosted on a dedicated YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCavb447TmldCICmikOnC9yQ>) so they are easily accessible to the global nursing community.

3 Discussion

The AI Nurses Network is being evaluated using an online survey and focus groups with nurses who take part in the new clinical research network, along with web analytics from the dedicated website. The network is helping create a vibrant community of nurses who actively research AI to improve patient care and is building capacity for more digitally enabled nurses in the NHS across the UK.

However, clinical research networks can be challenging to sustain over the long-term due to difficulties securing sustainable sources of funding, changing priorities in the health and care sector, time constraints amongst nursing researchers and practitioners, and barriers translating scientific evidence into professional practice [4]. To address some of these the AI Nurses Network is building links with national initiatives such as the AI Ambassadors network in NHS England, the Chief Nursing Informatics Officer Advisory Panel, and the NIHR Nursing and Midwifery team to help embed the new clinical research network in national health research infrastructure.

The long-term vision is to expand the network internationally by building collaborative links with European colleagues and others researching AI in nursing so that nurses worldwide can benefit from the resources and opportunities provided by the AI Nurses Network to improve patient care and population health through the innovative use of AI techniques and AI tools.

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